

HIBISCUS SABDARIFFA: "A COMPARATIVE PHYTOCHEMICALS AND ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY OF TWO VARIETIES"

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Abstract

This study investigated the comparative phytochemical composition and antidiabetic activity of two Hibiscus sabdariffa (red and white) varieties. Both varieties were analyzed for their bioactive components and hypoglycemic effects using methanol calyx extracts in rats with alloxan-induced diabetes. Phytochemical screening revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, and cardiac glycosides in both varieties, with the red variety exhibiting higher concentrations of tannins and flavonoids. The red variety also yielded a higher extractive value (9.65%) than the white variety (8.58%).

The activity of antidiabetic of the plants was assessed by monitoring post-treatment blood glucose levels. Both extracts demonstrated significant hypoglycemic effects, with the red variety demonstrating superior glucose-lowering efficacy at higher doses. This enhanced activity is attributed to its higher concentrations of flavonoids and phenolic compounds, which inhibit carbohydrate-digesting enzymes and mitigate oxidative stress.

The findings revealed that H. sabdariffa, particularly the white variety, has great potential as a natural antidiabetic agent. Further research is recommended to isolate and characterize the bioactive compounds and validate their therapeutic efficacy through clinical trials. This study highlights the importance of H. sabdariffa in the development of functional foods and nutraceuticals for the management of diabetes and related metabolic disorders.

Introduction.

Medicinal plants are a cornerstone of both curative and preventive healthcare for humans and are also a rich source of bioactive compounds (Lambert *et al.*, 1997; Thirumalai *et al.*, 2009; Rasool, 2012). Approximately 80% of the global population, especially in developing nations, relies on traditional medicine for their healthcare needs. Many individuals in these regions integrate conventional medicine with traditional remedies (Musila *et al.*, 2000; Mahwasane *et al.*, 2013; Kinyanjui *et al.*, 2014).

Two main varieties of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*—red and white—are widely cultivated for their medicinal, culinary, and economic applications. However, while the red variety has been extensively studied, the white variety remains relatively underexplored. This study aims to bridge this gap by comparing the phytochemical profiles and antidiabetic activities of the two varieties to evaluate their potential for managing HGS and related metabolic disorders.

Traditional medicines are often more accessible, affordable, and culturally aligned for rural communities in these countries (Popovic *et al.*, 2016). Traditional medicine remains vital in Sub-Saharan Africa, where healthcare infrastructure is limited to urban areas (Maroyi and Cheikhyouseef, 2015). Plant -based medicine has deep cultural roots, particularly in African societies (Petrovska, 2012).

Hibiscus sabdariffa, also as red and white roselle, belongs to the Malvaceae family and thrives in arid and semi-arid climates. Its creamy white calyces, greenish stems, and lanceolate leaves distinguish it from the red variety. Although less popular than the red variety, both *H. sabdariffa* varieties contain significant bioactive compounds with medicinal applications, including antioxidants, anti-inflammatory agents, and antidiabetic properties.

White *Hibiscus sabdariffa* is an annual shrub that grows up to a height of 2–3 m. The plant is distinguished by its creamy white calyces, greenish stems, and lanceolate leaves. The plant thrives in sandy loam soils with moderate rainfall, making it ideal for cultivation in arid and semi-arid regions. Its calyces are used in preparing beverages, and its leaves, seeds, and stems have diverse therapeutic applications (Edeoga *et al.*, 2006).

Methodology

Collection, identification, and processing

The plant material (calyces) was collected in Borno State, Nigeria. In November 2024

Preparation and extraction of plant matrix

The calyces were air dried at room temperature and ground using a wooden mortar and pestle. The powdered material was stored in an airtight container before extraction. The solvent used for the extraction was methanol. 1 kg of the powdered material was poured into a container, and methanol was added to it and allowed to macerate for 24 h. It was then filtered and air –dried on a tray. The process was repeated thrice to yield extracts.

Experimental Procedures

Phytochemical Screening

A small quantity of the extract was subjected to preliminary phytochemical screening and the following secondary metabolites were analyzed: alkaloids, saponin, terpenes/terpenoids, carbohydrates, flavonoids, glycosides, and fatty acids.

Test for Carbohydrates

a. Molish’s test

To 2 ml of plant sample extract, two drops of alcoholic solution of α - naphthol are added. The mixture is shaken well, and a few drops of concentrated sulfuric acid are slowly added along the sides of the test tube. A violet ring indicates the presence of carbohydrates in the sample. (Evans, 2002).

b. Fehling’s Test

The extract was dissolved in 2 ml of distilled water and filtered. The filtrate was heated with 5 ml of equal volumes of Fehling’s solutions A and B. The formation of a brick-red cuprous oxide precipitate indicates the presence of free reducing sugars, such as fructose or glucose (Evans, 2002).

c. Barfoed’s Test

The extract was dissolved in distilled water and filtered. 1 ml of the filtrate was then mixed with 1 ml of Barfoed's reagent in a test tube and then heated in a water bath for 2 min. A reddish precipitate of cuprous oxide was considered a positive test (Sofowora, 1993).

Test for alkaloids

a. Mayer's test

Two drops of Mayer's reagent were added to a few milliliters of plant sample extract along the sides of the test tube. Appearance of white creamy precipitate indicates the presence of alkaloids. (Evans, 2002).

b. Wagner's test

A few drops of Wagner's reagent were added to a few milliliters of plant extract along the sides of the test tube. A reddish-brown precipitate confirms alkaloid positivity (Wagner, 1993).

Test for Phenolic Compounds and Tannins

a. Ferric chloride test

A small quantity of the extract was dissolved in 5 ml of distilled water. A few drops of neutral 5% ferric chloride solution are added to this. A dark green color indicates the presence of phenolic compounds (Evans, 2002).

c. Lead acetate test

A small quantity of the extract was dissolved in distilled water, and 3 ml of 10% lead acetate solution was added to this solution. A bulky white precipitate indicates the presence of a phenolic compound. (Evans, 2002).

Test for the Saponin

A small quantity of the extract was diluted with distilled water. The suspension is shaken in a graduated cylinder for 15 min. A 2-cm layer of foam indicates saponin (Evans, 2002).

General test for glycosides

The glycoside sample (0.2g) was placed in a test tube, and 5 ml of dilute sulfuric acid was added. The solution was boiled in a water bath for 10-15 minutes followed by cooling and neutralization with 20% KOH. The mixture was divided into two portions as follows:

To the first portion, 5 ml of a mixture of Fehling's solutions A and B was added and boiled. The appearance of the brick red precipitate indicated the release of reducing sugar as a result of glycoside hydrolysis.

To the second portion, 3 ml of ferric chloride solution was added, and phenolic glycoside was released due to hydrolysis (Evans, 2002).

Acute Toxicity

The acute toxicity (LD₅₀) of the methanol calyx extract of *H. safdariffa* was determined using the OECD guideline in rats (OECD Test Guideline 425). Modified Lorke's method (Deora et al., 2010) was adopted in the study to evaluate the acute toxicity of the *H. safdariffa* extract following oral administration in Wistar strain albino rats, which was determined under the standard conditions and allowed free access to food and water. The animals (n = 2 per dose) were fasted for 4 h before the experiment. In phase one (i), the animals were administered the dose of the extract at 10 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 1000 mg/kg and observed for their mortality and signs of toxicity during the first 24 h. The dose was increased to 1600, 2900, and 5000 mg/kg in phase II.

Determination of the antidiabetic effects of *H. sabdariffa*

Thirty rats weighing between 150 and 289 g were grouped into six groups each containing five rats. Groups 1 and 2 were used as normal (negative) control and diabetic (positive) control, respectively, and groups 3, 4, 5, and 6 were induced with diabetes using alloxan at a dose of 150 mg/kg. The animals were fasted overnight, and their baseline blood glucose level was measured before diabetes induction. Their blood glucose levels were measured at 24 and 48 h after alloxan administration. A blood glucose level of 200 mg/dl and above is considered to be diabetic. The animals were regrouped according to the increase in their blood glucose levels. Group 3 was

administered insulin at a dose of 0.5 IU/kg body weight, whereas groups 4, 5, and 6 were administered the plant extract orally at doses of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg body weight respectively. Their blood glucose levels were measured subsequently at 3, 6, 12, and 24 h.

Blood glucose determination

Accu-Chek® (an active trademark of Roche Mannheim, Mannheim, Germany) was used for blood glucose determination. The code on the glucometer was set to correspond with that on the glucometer strips. This is to avoid errors and ensure the accuracy of the results. The tail of each rat was pricked with a lancet, and a drop of blood was collected on the strip and then inserted into the glucometer, and the readings on the screen of the glucometer were recorded in mg/dl.

Statistical Analysis

Data obtained from this study were analyzed using one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) to determine the relationship between the means of the variables using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 16 and the results were expressed as mean and standard error of the mean (Mean ± SEM). A P-value < 0.05 is considered significant.

Results and Discussion

Plant extraction

The extractive values for the crude methanol calyces extract of both white and red *H. sabdariffa* from 1 kg of plant material were 85.80 g and 96.50g, respectively (Table 1.0).

Table 1.0 Yield of crude white methanol leaf extracts. *sabdariffa*

S/N solvent yield (g) percentage (%)

1. Methanol 85.8 8.58

Table 1.0 Yield of crude methanol leaf extracts of Red *H. sabdariffas*

S/N solvent yield (g) percentage (%)

1. Methanol 96.5 9.65

Fig 1: Yield of crude methanol leaf extracts of both *H. sabdariffa* species

Preliminary Phytochemical Screening

Phytochemical analysis of the methanol calyces extract of *H. sabdariffa* revealed the presence of alkaloids, carbohydrate, cardiac glycoside, flavonoids, saponins, and tannins and the absence of general glycoside (Table 2.1).

Table 2: Preliminary Phytochemical Screening of Crude Methanol Calyces Extracts of Red and White *H. sabdariffa*

S/No.	Phytochemicals	Specific Test	RHS (Inference)	WHS (Inference)
1	Carbohydrates	Molish's test	+	+
		Barfoed's test	+	+
2	Tannins	The ferric chloride test	+	+
		10% HCl	+	-
3	Steroids/Triterpenoids	Liebermann-Burchard's test	+	+
4	Saponins	Frothing test	+	+
5	Flavonoids	The ferric chloride test	+	+
		Sodium hydroxide test	+	-
6	Alkaloids	Mayer's test	+	+

Key: + = detected, - = not detected, RHS= Red *H. sabdariffa*, WHS= White *H. sabdariffa*

Acute Toxicity Study

There was no rat death in the first phase at the doses of 10 mg/kg, 100 mg/kg, and 1000 mg/kg body weight of the ethanol flower extract of *H. sabdariffa*, as well as in the second phase at the doses of 1600 mg/kg, 2900 mg/kg,

and 5000 mg/kg body weight of the extract (Table 4.3). The LD₅₀ was greater than 5000 mg/kg body weight orally.

Table 3: Oral acute toxicity of crude methanol extracts of the Calyces of Red and White *H. sabdariffa*.

Experimental phases	Dose (mg/kg)	Death observation within 24 hours
Phase I		
	10	0/2
	100	0/2
	1000	0/2
Phase II		
	1600	0/2
	2900	0/2
	5000	0/2
LD ₅₀	>5000	

Table 4: Hypoglycemic effect of *H. sabdariffa* (white) methanol extracts (calyx) on glucose levels in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

Group	Treatment (mg/kg)	A (mg/dl)	B (mg/dl)	Glucose level after treatment				
				1 h	3 h	6 h	24 h	48 h
CT	NS(2ml/kg)	109.2±3.8	112.6±2.1 ^x	112.8±2.1	108.2±3.2	111.0±2.8	107.0±2.9	111.4±2.1
DC	NS(2ml/kg)	108.6±5.6	485.4±2.6	520.0±20.5	538.4±14.6	531.0±3.9	557.2±12.8	580.0±6.1
Insulin	0.75(iu/kg)	111.6±3.0	395.8±7.4	165.4±71.5	116.0±40.0	179.6±2.3	262.8±22.2	384.6±35.2
WSL	(100mg/kg)	121.2±8.2	382.6±5.1	469.8±78.8	586.6±11.5 ^β	420.8±2.9 ^β	293.4±44.6 ^β	519.8±31.9 ^β
WS	(200mg/kg)	117.6±8.8	408.2±5.0	462.0±63.1	544.2±48.0 ^β	498.6±6.9 ^β	204.6±20.4 ^β	295.2±48.2 ^β
WSH	(400mg/kg)	99.4±2.2	407.8±5.1	502.2±43.8	457.8±23.3	369.0±4.2	202.0±16.5	425.6±46.0

Key: A glucose level after 24 h of fasting, B glucose level 72 h after alloxan, x glucose level 72 h after fasting, CT = Control, DC diabetic control, LD low dose, MD moderate dose, HD = high dose, WSH=*H. sabdariffa*, n = 5, Student's t-test, *= p<0.05 (significant compared with DC), β = p<0.05 (significant compared with insulin).

Table 5: Hypoglycemic effect of *H. sabdariffa* (Red) methanol extracts (calyx) on glucose levels in alloxan-induced diabetic rats

Group	Treatment(mg/kg)	A (mg/dl)	B (mg/dl)	Glucose level after treatment				
				1 h	3 h	6 h	24 h	48 h
CT	NS(2ml/kg)	109.2±3.8	112.6±2.1 ^x	112.8±2.1	108.2±3.2	111.0±2.8	107.0±2.9	111.4±2.1
DC	NS(2ml/kg)	108.6±5.6	485.4±22.6	520.0±2.0	538.4±14.6	531.0±13.9	557.2±12.8	580.0±6.1
Insulin	0.75(iu/kg)	111.6±3.0	395.8±74.6	165.4±7.5	116.0±40.0	179.6±32.3	262.8±22.2	384.6±35.2
RSLD	(100mg/kg±±)	115.4±7.2	390.2±45.5	350.6±4.0	310.4±35.8 ^β	280.5±28.6 ^β	254.4±30.2 ^β	313.6±25.4 ^β
RSMD	(200mg/kg)	112.8±6.4	412.5±52.1	320.4±3.8	250.2±30.4 ^β	190.6±25.2 ^β	184.2±18.4 ^β	280.4±22.1 ^β
RSHD	(400mg/kg)	105.6±8.2	405.2±48.6	280.8±4.2	195.4±28.2	175.2±22.5	157.6±15.4	223.6±46.0

Key: A glucose level after 24 h of fasting, B glucose level 72 h after alloxan, x glucose level 72 h after fasting, CT = Control, DC diabetic control, LD low dose, MD moderate dose, HD = high dose, RHS=*H. sabdariffa*, n = 5, Student's t-test, * = p<0.05 (significant compared with DC), β = p<0.05 (significant compared with insulin).

Discussions

Table 1 shows methanol extraction yields of 8.6% for the white species and 9.7% for the red species of *H. sabdariffa* calyces. The red species not only produced a higher absolute yield (96.5 g vs. 85.8 g) but, also a higher percentage yield than the white species. This pattern is consistent with established data from the literature, where red variants of *H. sabdariffa* typically yield more extractable material due to their higher content of phenolic compounds and anthocyanins (Chatepa *et al.*, 2023). Recent studies on methanol extraction of hibiscus leaves have reported yields ranging from 7.9% to 16.2% (w/w, dry basis), depending on the species, extraction conditions, and solvent composition. For *H. sabdariffa*, red calyces yield of 28%–31% (higher due to calyx composition) and leaves yields of 18.6% (white) and 19.7% (red) are well within the expected range (Yagi *et al.*, 2023).

Table 2 shows that crude methanol extracts of both white and red *Hibiscus sabdariffa* calyces are rich in diverse phytochemicals, with minor differences based on specific tests (e.g., sodium hydroxide test for flavonoids in white, positive in red; methanol test for tannins in white, negative in red). These results are consistent with those of the current research, which confirms the presence of similar phytochemical classes, such as phenols, flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids, glycosides, and terpenoids, in *H. sabdariffa* calyces, aligning with the thesis findings (Abdulhameed *et al.*, 2023; Alhassan *et al.*, 2023; Elhassan *et al.*, 2023).

As shown in Table 3, the oral acute toxicity (LD50) of the methanol extract (calyces) of both *H. sabdariffa* varieties was greater than 5000 mg/kg body weight, indicating that it is relatively non-toxic on acute exposure. This study is similar to the work of Jawla *et al.* (2012), who, reported that stepwise doses of the methanol stem bark extract were administered from 300 mg/kg to 5000 mg/kg orally, and no considerable signs of toxicity were observed.

Tables 4 and 5 also reveal that the methanol calyces extract of white and red *H. sabdariffa* varieties shows significant hypoglycemic activity at doses of 100, 200, and 400 mg/kg.

Compared with the diabetic control, all significant hypoglycemic effects were observed at 24 and 48 h, respectively, for low doses of the extracts (100 mg/kg). Whereas the most significant reduction was observed at 24 and 48 h for high doses compared to DC, and the middle doses were less effective compared to HD but more effective than LD at the same hours after oral administration of the extract. Compared with insulin (drug control), there was a significant decrease in blood glucose level than the extract in 1, 3, and 6 h. There was also a significant decrease when the extract was compared with insulin at 1, 3, and 6 h at all doses and at the lowest dose (100 mg/kg) at 48 h. The antidiabetic effect of methanol calyces extract is dose-dependent considering the order of significant decrease in blood glucose level and is more potent than regular insulin at 8% in 24 h. The red variety is more potent than its white counterpart. This is consistent with a study that indicated that aqueous and ethanolic extracts of *H. sabdariffa* (calyces and flowers) effectively lower plasma glucose levels in diabetic animal models, often showing a sustained effect that improves glucose tolerance over time (Okonkwo *et al.*, 2021). Another study also showed a dose-dependent effect, where higher concentrations lead to proportional improvement (Al-Dosari *et al.*, 2020).

Conclusion

The comparative evaluation of white and red Hibiscus sabdariffa varieties reveals significant medicinal potential in both varieties, attributed to their bioactive phytochemical compositions. Although both varieties exhibited similar phytochemical profiles, the Red variety demonstrated comparatively stronger hypoglycemic activity at higher doses which make it to be may be more effective as a natural antidiabetic remedy. These results support the traditional use of *H. sabdariffa* for diabetes management and underscore its importance as a source of natural antioxidants and therapeutic agents, especially in resource-limited regions.

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Author Declaration

The authors hereby declare that the work presented in this article is original and has not been previously published.

References.

- Burnham, T., Wickersham, R., & Novak, K. (2002). *The review of natural products* (3rd ed). St. Louis, MO: *Facts and Comparisons*.
- Da-Costa-Rocha I, Bonnlaender B, Sievers H, Pischel, I., & Heinrich, M. (2014). Hibiscus sabdariffa L.–A phytochemical and pharmacological review. *Food Chemistry*, 165, 424-443.
- Diane, L. M., Chen, O., Saltzman, E., & Blumberg, J. B. (2009). Hibiscus sabdariffa L. tea (tisane) lowers blood pressure in prehypertensive and mildly hypertensive adults. *Journal of Nutrition*, 140(2), 298-303. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jn.2009.09.016>
- Dickel, M. L., Rates, S. M., & Ritter, M. R. (2007). Plants popularly used for losing weight purposes in Porto Alegre, South Brazil. *Journal of Ethnopharmacology*, 109(1), 60–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jep.2007.01.013>.

- Edeoga, H. O., Okwu, D. E., & Mbaebie, B. O. (2006). Phytochemical constituents of some Nigerian medicinal plants. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 4(7), 685-688.
- Eltayeib, A. A., & Hamade, H. (2014). Phytochemical and chemical composition of water extract of Hibiscus Sabdariffa (red karkadee calyces) in North Kordofan state. *International Journal Advanced Research Chemistry Science*, 1(6), 10-13.
- Fakeye, T.O., et al. (2009). Toxic effects of oral administration of Hibiscus sabdariffa calyx extracts. *Phytotherapy Research*, 23(3), 412–416. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.phyto.2009.09.016>
- Fakeye, Pal A., Bawankule DU, Yadav, N.P., and Khanuja, S.P. (2009). Toxic effects of oral administration of extracts of dried calyx of Hibiscus sabdariffa Linn. (Malvaceae). *Phytotherapy Research* 2009; 23:412–16.
- Farombi E, Ige O. Hypolipidemic and antioxidant effects of ethanolic extract from dried calyx of Hibiscus sabdariffa in alloxan- induced diabetic rats. *J Clin Invest*. 2012; 57: e0150. *Fundam. Clin. Pharmacol*. 2007; 21 (6):601-9.
- Fernández-Arroyo S, Rodríguez-Medina IC, BeltránDebón R, et al. Quantification of the polyphenolic fraction and in vitro antioxidant and in vivo anti- hyperlipemic activities of Hibiscus sabdariffa aqueous extract. *Food Res Int*. 2012; 44(5):1490-5. doi: 10.1016/j.foodres.2011.03.040.
- Fouda, A. M. Daba, M. H., & Dahab, G. M. (2007). Inhibitory effects of aqueous extract of Hibiscus sabdariffa on contractility of the rat bladder and uterus. *Canadian Journal of Physiology and Pharmacology*, 85(10), 1020–1031. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cjp.2007.10.1016>
- Gaya, I. B., Mohammad, O. M. A. Suleiman, A. M., Maje, M. I., & Adekunle, A. B. (2009). Toxicological and lactogenic studies on the seeds of Hibiscus Sabdariffa Linn (Malvaceae) extract on serum prolactin levels of albino wistar rats. *The Internet Journal of Endocrinology*, 5(2), e0186. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jendo.2009.01.015>.
- Gibbon, D., & Pain, A. (1985). Crops of the drier regions of the tropics (1st Ed.). Longman, England: *English Language Book Society*.
- Ismail, A., Ikram, E. H. K., and Nazri, H. S. M. (2008). Roselle (Hibiscus sabdariffa L.) seeds nutritional composition protein quality and health benefits. *Food*, 2(1), 1–16.
- Jabeur I, Pereira E, Caleja C, Calhelha RC, Soković M, Catarino L, et al. Exploring the chemical and bioactive properties of Hibiscus sabdariffa L. calyces from GuineaBissau (West Africa). *Food Funct*. 2019; 10(4):2234-43. doi: 10.1039/c9fo00287a.
- Keyata EO, Tola YB, Bultosa G, Forsido SF. Phytochemical contents, antioxidant activity and functional properties of Raphanus sativus L, Eruca sativa L. and Hibiscus sabdariffa L. growing in Ethiopia. *Heliyon*. 2021; 7(1):e05939. doi: 10.1016/j.heliyon.2021.e05939.

- Kochhar, S. L. (1986). *Tropical crops: a textbook of economic botany*. London, UK: *Macmillan Publishers Limited*.
- Leung, A. Y., & Foster, S. (1996). *Encyclopedia of common natural ingredients used in food, drugs, and cosmetics* (2nd ed.). New York: *John Wiley and Sons*.
- Lieu, P. T., Heiskala, M., Peterson, P. A., & Yang, Y. (2001). *The roles of iron in health and disease. Molecular Aspects Medical*. 22:1-87.
- Lin HH, Huang HP, Huang CC, Chen JH, Wang CJ. Hibiscus polyphenol-rich extract induces apoptosis in human gastric carcinoma cells via p53 phosphorylation and p38 MAPK/ FasL cascade pathway. *Mol Carcinog*. 2005;43(2):86-99. doi: 10.1002/mc.20103
- Liu, C.L., Wang, J.M., Chu, C.Y., Cheng, M.T., Tseng, T.H., 2002. In vivo protective effect of protocatechuic acid on tert-butyl hydroperoxide-induced rat hepatotoxicity. *Food and Chemical Toxicology*, 40(5), 635–641.
- Marisca EG, Hanna SWK, Wahyu W. α - Glucosidase and α -Amylase Inhibitory Activities of Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) ethanol extract. *Mol Cell Biomed Sci*. 2017; 1(1):34-40
- McKay, D. L., & Blumberg, J. B. (2010). A review of the bioactivity and potential health benefits of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. tea (roselle). *Phytotherapy Research*, 24(1), 1-8.
- Mohammed, A., Ibrahim, M., & Usman, B. (2009). Phytochemical screening and antimicrobial activity of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. extracts. *Research Journal of Pharmaceutical, Biological and Chemical Sciences*, 1(4), 64-71.
- Mohammed, A., Tanko, Y., Okasha, M. A., Magaji, M. G., & Yaro, A. H. (2007). Effects of aqueous leaves extract of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* on blood glucose levels of normoglycemic and alloxan-induced diabetic Wistar rats. *International Journal of Biological & Chemical Sciences*, 1(3), 255-260.
- Morton, J. F. (1987). Roselle. *Fruits of warm climates*, 281-286.
- Morton, J. F. (1987). *Fruits of warm climates. Florida: Flair Books*.
- Mungole A, Chaturvedi A. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. a rich source of secondary metabolites. *Int J Pharm Sci Rev Res*. 2011; 6(1):83-7.
- Neuwinger, H. (2000). *African traditional medicine*. Stuttgart: *Medpharm Scientific Publication*.
- Nguyen, T., Armentano, L., & Sanders, J. (2010). Anti-inflammatory effects of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* extract: A randomized controlled trial. *International Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 12(3), 112-121.
- Nyam KL, Leao SY, Tan CP, Long K (2014). Functional properties of roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) seed and its application as bakery product. *J Food Sci Technol*. 2014; 51(12):3830-7. doi: 10.1007/s13197-012-0902-x.

- Nyam, K. L., Leao, S. Y., Tan, C. P., & Long, K. (2014). Functional properties of roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) seed and its application as a bakery product. *Journal of Food Science and Technology*, 51(12), 3830–3837. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfst.2014.09.007>
- Onyenekwe PC, Ajani EO, Ameh, D.A., & Gamammiel, K.S. (1999). Antihypertensive effect of roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa*) calyx infusion in spontaneously hypertensive rats and a comparison of its toxicity with that in Wistar rats. *Cell Biochemical Function*, 17, 199–206.
- Pacome, O.A., Bernard, D.N., Sekou, D., Joseph, D.A., David, N.D., Mongomake, K., & Hilaire, K.T. (2014). Phytochemical and antioxidant activity of Roselle (*Hibiscus Sabdariffa* L.) petal extracts. *Research Journal of Pharmacology Biology Chemistry Science*, 5(2), 1453-1465.
- Padmaja, H., Sruthi, S., & Vangalapati, M. (2014). Review on *Hibiscus sabdariffa*—A valuable herb. *International Journal Pharmacology of Life Science*, 5(8), 3747-3752.
- Peng, C.H.; Chyau, C.C.; Chan, K.C.; Chan, T.H.; Wang, C.J.; Huang, C.N. *Hibiscus sabdariffa* Polyphenolic Extract Inhibits Hyperglycemia, Hyperlipidemia, and Glycation-Oxidative Stress while Improving Insulin Resistance. *J. Agri. Food Chem.* 2011;59 (18):9901-9.
- Peng, C.H., et al. (2011). *Hibiscus sabdariffa* polyphenolic extract inhibits hyperglycemia, hyperlipidemia, and glycation-oxidative stress while improving insulin resistance. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 59(18), 9901-9909.
- S. Pimentel-Moral, I. Borrás-Linares, J. Lozano-Sánchez, D. Arráez-Román D, Martínez-Férez A, Segura-Carretero A. Supercritical CO₂ extraction of bioactive compounds from *Hibiscus sabdariffa*. *J Supercrit Fluids*. 2019; 147:213-21. doi: 10.1016/j.supflu.2018.11.005.
- Pimentel-Moral, S., et al. (2019). Supercritical CO₂ extraction of bioactive compounds from *Hibiscus sabdariffa*. *J. Superc. Fluids*, 147, 213–221.
- Puro, K., Sunjukta, R., Samir, S., Ghatak, S., Shakuntala & Sen, A. (2014). Medicinal uses of roselle plant (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.): a mini review. *Indian Journal of Hill Farming*, 27(1), pp. 57-76.
- Sharaf, A. (1962). *The pharmacological characteristics of Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. *Plantar Medical*, 10, 48–52.
- Takeda, N., & Yasui, Y. (1985). Identification of mutagenic substances in roselle, elderberry, and safflower colors. *Agric Biol Chem*, 49, 1851–1852.
- Tsai P-J, McIntosh J, Pearce P, Camden B, Jordan BR. Anthocyanin and antioxidant capacity in Roselle (*Hibiscus sabdariffa* L.) extract. *Food Res Int.* 2002;35(4):351-6. doi: 10.1016/s0963-\ 9969(01)00129-6.
- Tseng, et al. (1997). Protective effects of dried flower extracts of *H. sabdariffa* L. against oxidative stress. *Food and Chemical Toxicology* 35:1159–1164

- Tseng, T.H., Kao, E.S., Chu, H.Y., Chou, F.P., Lin, W.H.W., Wang, C.J., 1997. Protective effects of dried flower extracts of *Hibiscus sabdariffa* L. against oxidative stress in rat primary hepatocytes. *Food Chem. Toxicol.* 35, 1159–1164.
- Tseng, T. H., Wang, C. J., Kao, E. S., & Chu, C. Y. (1996). Hibiscus protocatechuic acid protects against oxidative damage induced by tertbutylhydroperoxide in rat primary hepatocytes. *Chemistry and Biology Interact.*, 101(2), 137-148.